

**Integrating computational and statistical methods into the Humanities:
Investigating tourism discourse with empirical social semiotics**

Elena MATTEI, Ca' Foscari, University of Venice, Italy

This paper analyzes the Instagram and website visual content posted by three popular English-speaking tourism boards, namely Tourism Ireland, Destination Canada, and Tourism Western Australia, with a semiotic approach involving manual annotation. By developing a framework integrating empirical multimodality, systemic functional linguistics and corpus studies, the paper shows how data-driven, customized taxonomies may foster evidence-based discourse interpretations and help develop analytical skills to actively interpret signs and decode purposes, which is key in an increasingly artificial context in which algorithms organize and create data through automatic entity recognition. Specifically, results reveal that Instagram imagery prioritizes emotional engagement over concrete information, promoting instant gratification and escape through highly positive, visually appealing positive expectations about leisure experiences of passive contemplation and extra-ordinary, peaceful solitary fruition of nature. This emphasis impacts digital literacy and fosters a consumerist mindset within neoliberal societies, highlighting the necessity for a systematic and critical engagement with visual narratives.

Keywords: Corpus Linguistics; Instagram Tourism Discourse; Multimodality; Systemic Functional Linguistics; Visual Communication

1. Introduction

One of the greatest challenges the humanities have faced in the recent decades is the adoption of quantitative measures to study social phenomena and provide reproducible, data-driven interpretations, like many fields in the so-called “hard sciences” (Krippendorff, 2004, p. 215). This challenge, however, demands the development of theoretical, analytical, and technological tools, as well as methodological frameworks suitable for humanities research.

In the realm of interdisciplinary Digital Humanities (DH), scholars have been exploring specifically new computational approaches based on machine-learning and Artificial Intelligence methods, in an attempt to critically understand the implications of automatic content analysis and entity recognition, as well as their role in the spread of biased content through unsupervised annotation of large datasets (Sayers, 2018).

From a linguistic perspective, corpus analysis has been crucial to uncover concealed intentions through the detection of patterns of language use, shedding light on the perpetuation and legitimization of information (McEnery & Hardie, 2011; Taylor & Marchi, 2018). These quantitative methods provide fresh insights into meaning creation processes and their role in shaping viewpoints and behaviors. Discourse analysts, particularly, leverage these advancements to examine asymmetric communication and power dynamics, often incorporating social semiotics (multimodality) and systemic functional linguistics (SFL) (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014; Kress, 2010), as language resources are increasingly combined with other modes of communication in the digital realm (Stöckl et al., 2020).

In the domain of tourism discourse, scholars have been increasingly turning to multimodal, socio-semiotic investigations to tackle the complexity of digital promotional communication and approach it with adequate methodologies that explore the relationship between visual and linguistic meaning-making choices in context. Despite the groundbreaking, corpus-based linguistic insights and pioneering multimodal results presented in existing research (Bianchi, 2017; Francesconi, 2014; Hallet & Kaplan-Weinger, 2010; Maci, 2020; Manca, 2016; Manca, 2017), and the proved impact of imagery on perceptions and purchasing behavior (Mitchell & Mitchell, 1994; Shuqair & Cragg, 2017), a systematic and comprehensive analysis of visual and textual meaning creation has not yet been conducted in Instagram (IG) tourism discourse. The latter, thus, represents an important research avenue for multimodal analysts, and offers the opportunity to support marketing studies on IG customer perception with an understanding of how imagery channels desires for escape and imagination at the social and semiotic level (Huang & Su, 2018; Mattei, 2023b).

This paper seeks to demonstrate how the testing of theoretical assumptions through categorization and inter-annotation data may lead to evidence-based, sociological interpretations of patterns of data, or 'strategies' clustering in tourism discourse. Indeed, it seeks to provide a new framework for the analysis of promotional images shared by travel boards by integrating systemic functional linguistics and social semiotic theories, to allow for the creation of a tagging system that can enable the quantification and measurement of various visual strategies across images and communication platforms, shedding light on novel ways of providing instant gratification and creating desire by leveraging tourists' need to escape into the unknown and extra-ordinary in our postmodern society (Urry & Larsen, 2011). In other words, it highlights how the development of suitable theoretical and methodological tools can assist researchers and students in the analysis and production of signs, leading to an informed and active social understanding of how ideologies are legitimized. From a scientific standpoint, this empirical and interdisciplinary approach may uncover generic variations that are influenced by socioeconomic factors, which

are relevant to an understanding of how the tourism industry operates and continues to profit in the post-Fordist, consumerist society.

The paper is structured into five main sections. Section 2 provides the background for the study and explains the mixed methodological approach, including the use of SRI Tagging software, adopted for a multimodal investigation of modern tourism narratives. It discusses the integration of various theories into a comprehensive, multisemiotic, and socially informed data-driven perspective, transcending disciplinary boundaries for a fresh approach to tourism discourse analysis. This section draws from systemic functional and corpus linguistics, social semiotics, and empirical multimodality, applied to the socioeconomic context of tourism across various digital media. Section 3 describes the tools and methods used in the project, with a focus on the tree tagging system designed for annotating and measuring quantitatively visual promotional strategies and the software created for the conduction of such tasks. Section 4 elaborates on the empirical process of visual annotation and statistical analysis, which is shown to lead to reliable and innovative interpretations of information from a sociological perspective. To do so, the section illustrates the categorization of annotations and results through the concept of metafunctional meaning, demonstrating how its instantiation varies depending on the context and medium of dissemination, including the purpose and audience's behavior on digital platforms. This section also outlines the scientific and educational implications of the methodology, offering insights into the development of critical analytical skills through empirical multimodal discourse analysis.

2. Background

The theoretical framework, tools and sample of data presented in this paper are extracted from a corpus-based study of contemporary trends of effective tourism strategies for the digital promotion of holiday destinations. The project, which combines a multimodal and multidisciplinary approach, examined specifically if and how discourse specialists shape positive expectations about the genuine, pristine and unknown, emphasizing travel as a solution to human desires. This was achieved by leveraging prospective tourists' social desire for exclusivity, control, and a perceived deliberate choice to engage emotionally with extraordinary experiences (Urry & Larsen, 2011).

The study involved the manual annotation and empirical as well as qualitative analyses of corpora consisting of static images and written texts retrieved from three popular English-speaking tourism boards' Instagram accounts and official websites: (1) Tourism Ireland, (2) Destination Canada, and (3) Tourism Western Australia. The data was uploaded on *SRI Tagging and Sketch Engine*

software for multisemiotic annotation and analysis. However, for the purpose of this study, only the process of visual tagging and analysis is reported.¹

The systematic categorization of the visuo-linguistic attributes observed through data-driven tagging models building on the concept of metafunction facilitated the quantification and statistical evaluation of the frequency and variability of semiotic resources for meaning creation across different modes and digital platforms. In this sense, this study unveiled the emergence of an Instagram, image-centric genre of tourism discourse (Bateman, 2014) that focuses on the stimulation of imagination and irrational response through less informative but highly evocative, evaluative orchestrations (Stöckl et al., 2020). In line with previous results in tourism research, this study shows how semiotic representations and visuo-linguistic patterns of meaning are leveraged to subtly encode, mold the postmodern tourist gaze at leisure experiences, thus representing a form of social control to manipulate perceptions and legitimate (pre)consumption practices such as daydreaming (Francesconi, 2014; Manca, 2016). Specifically, the multidisciplinary approach helped to trace the emergence of an image-centric Romantic gaze in contemporary media and illustrates the benefits of implementing a statistical and social semiotics approach to validate these assumptions and provide data-driven interpretations.

The paper, therefore, transcends disciplinary boundaries to understand the visual turn, and understand its challenges and opportunities. Noticing the emergence of an image-centric Romantic gaze to manipulate the digital tourist, the paper argues that photography, even before the Internet era, was recognized for its ability to influence views and evoke emotions due to its perceptual resemblance to external experience and the unmediated nature of images (Barthes, 1972; Mitchell & Mitchell, 1994). In recent times, photographs have become persuasive tools that appear as reflections of reality and emotionally impactful products, as they cater to postmodern individuals' driving desires for certainty, simplicity and fulfillment in a visually persuasive digital world (Debord, 1977; Manovich, 2017; Messaris, 1997; Shuqair & Cragg, 2017). They are, therefore, assigned to the role of facilitating "rapid delivery, ubiquitous availability and the instant gratification of desires" in a rapidly changing and uncertain world (Tomlinson, 2007, p. 74).

The spread and increasing accessibility of digital platforms has soon convinced marketers to rely on imagery to craft highly evaluative, emotional content and attract postmodern users, who have limited time resources but unlimited access to abundant information (Ayeh et al., 2012; Hays et al., 2012; Leung et al., 2013). This content, indeed, encourages instant and often unconscious reactions to aesthetically appealing material, which represents a means to

validate and channel socially driven needs for social validation, common ground and eventually consumerism (Kress, 2010).

In the context of tourism discourse, the technological advances and emergent role of digital images as 'aesthetic symbols with an aura of indexicality' have been shown to be leveraged to foster a nostalgic and romantic perception of travel destinations that goes beyond mass-targeted gazes (Mattei, 2023a). Sociology and linguistic studies confirm that this trend aligns with the postmodern preference for solitary escape from over-regulated, oversocialized routines and pre-packaged holiday consumption into the calming and controlled stimulation of the senses in pristine, unfamiliar environments, i.e., without human footprint (Urry & Larsen, 2011; Maci, 2020). Instagram and similar platforms, thus, play a crucial role in disseminating images that stimulate anticipation of idealized and exclusive experiences and associated emotions, whereas the presence of human subjects is considered to demystify the apparent eternity and beauty of unchanged, natural environment (Garrod, 2009; Gotti et al., 2017; Zeng, 2013). However, quantitative studies on the impact and role of the visual mode in the perpetuation of such manipulating expectations are rarely undertaken, or are conducted in the field of automatic content analysis with varying research purposes.

We may argue that the fast-growing, digital economy of signs poses challenges for both humanists and computer scientists, as they both share an interest in categorizing semiotic elements in the digital sphere. While humanities scholars aim to understand its societal implications, computer scientists need to make data storage flawless and efficient, sometimes leaving aside considerations about the biases intrinsic to machine-based replications of categorizations. Without critical awareness and analytical skills, content creators and consumers on social platforms like Instagram may passively conform to prevailing norms and narratives, potentially compromising their own individual privacy and freedom of choice.

To address the complexity of the visual and multisemiotic economy of signs and its manipulative power from a discourse perspective, then, novel analytical tools are required. There is the need, perhaps, to develop a computer-based, statistical approach to digital imagery in the light of empirical social semiotics. As mentioned in the introduction, linguistics trends of corpus analysis and sociosemiotic investigations have paved the way for innovative approaches that expand beyond linguistics to encompass the analysis of various types of signs. Notably, Kress' (2010) social semiotic approach to multimodality provides a valid framework for a systematic and critical understanding of the yet undeciphered processes of visual meaning making in relation to linguistic semiotic resources. He does so by relying on the notion of meta-function, with which one may explore what functions signs fulfill to achieve communicative

aims, including (1) the framing of external experiences and internalization of events, and (2) manipulation of both perceptions and attitudes in the digital sphere. An overview of Kress' approach to the analysis of the visual mode is provided in Appendix A, including an empirically based adaptation of the Grammar of Visual Design (Insulander & Lindstrand, 2013; Kress, 2010; Mattei, 2023a; Pflaeging et al., 2021).

Despite Kress's pioneering work in the analysis of visual and multisemiotic meaning, his theoretical approach raises questions about its degree of objectivity and reproducibility in the investigation of large and specific visual data. His emphasis on the role of social context in sign-making, indeed, becomes problematic when trying to achieve a scientific perspective that is free from subjective or theory-based interpretations (Bateman et al., 2017).

Scholars in semiotics acknowledge specifically that this approach cannot be suitable for understanding visual signs, which are primarily icons that signify through their perceptual resemblance to external reality (Bateman, 2018). A visual analysis solely based on images' alleged, symbolic and socially attached value may indeed lack objectivity and scientific reliability, and this is especially true when applied without empirical testing of theoretical assumptions on large datasets, potentially leading to inaccurate interpretations.

The proposed alternative is to classify and analyze modes separately based on (1) their material forms, i.e., related to sensory perception and physical properties, and 2) their (social) semiotic forms, which are related to meanings given by individuals (Bateman, 2021). In other words, a data-informed analysis of mode affordances can empirically demonstrate the role of modes in constructing social and metafunctional meaning. To analyze imagery effectively, a 'grammar' of visual design should not be applied without empirical testing and data-driven adaptations of frameworks, as to avoid imposing classifications and interpretations without verification (Bateman, 2019).

Statistical detection and quantification of patterns in material regularities provide, then, fertile ground for contextualized discourse analysis of specific communicative events. This procedure, eventually, allows for the interpretation of 'semiotic traces' as regularities of social use and purpose and leads to a deep understanding of generic shifts (Bateman, 2014).

In conclusion, we may argue that the complex and visually oriented nature of contemporary narratives—including tourism discourse—requires substantial efforts at different levels:

- Theory: linguistics-based theory adaptations;
- Method: empirical detection of material forms as separated from the sociological interpretation of data;

- Analysis: systematic testing of categories through (inter)annotation procedures.

This multilayered approach may provide a more objective understanding of how signs function in digital tourism narratives. The procedure that unveiled new generic trends in Instagram, image-centric, and website persuasive discourse is outlined in the next section.

3. Method

In order to shed light on statistically measured patterns of strategies of contemporary tourism narratives, a series of computational methods were implemented. This section offers an overview of the process of multimodal data collection (3.1), annotation of variables, or tags, related to visual entities (3.2), and the use of the software SRI Tagging developed for manual annotation and statistical analysis of visual corpora (3.3). This section is key as it provides an example of computational implementation and statistical testing of theory-based tagging systems on datasets, thus adapting existing theories to data specificities in terms of genre and discourse.

3.1. Data

For this DH study, three popular tourist boards situated in English-speaking countries were selected. Specifically, the research gathered multimodal data consisting of static imagery and written text, from two primary communication platforms:

- Instagram, used to raise brand awareness and establish an emotional attachment through content sharing, and
- the official websites, which also offer booking opportunities.

The six multimodal sub-corpora were collected in 2019 through a combination of methods, including (1) the use of Instagram's application programming interface (API) to retrieve six months' worth of Instagram posts for each tourist board, (2) web scraping, and (3) a web crawling procedure provided by the text-mining software *Sketch Engine* (Kilgarriff et al., 2014). Following this data collection, all sub-corpora underwent a thorough cleaning and deduplication process—through uses of regular expressions—and both quantitative and qualitative analysis through different software and corpus techniques.

Tables 1 to 3 (Mattei, 2023a, pp. 5-6) present a breakdown of the visual and written sub-corpora, categorized by tourist board and their respective communication channels. The tables also illustrate the composition of the six sub-corpora of written language, grouped according to channels, and include details such as the number of tokens (the smallest units in a corpus, including

words, digits, punctuation), total word count, types/token ratio (TTR), and the distribution of tokens (%) within each sub-corpus.

Table 1
Subdivision of Visual Sub-Corpora According to Tourist Board and Channel

Tourist Board	No. of Images (IG Posts)	No. of Images (Official Websites)	No. of Total Images per Tourist Board
Tourism Ireland	126	200	326
Destination Canada	180	160	340
Tourism Western Australia	178	158	336
Total	484	518	1002

Table 2
Subdivision of Written Sub-Corpora According to Tourist Board on the Official Website

Website Corpus	Tokens	Words	% (Tokens)	Types/Token Ratio (TTR)
Tourism Ireland	745,251	36,482	62.9%	4.9
Destination Canada	406,084	26,366	34.2%	6.5
Tourism Western Australia	34,094	5,399	2.9%	15.8

Table 3
Subdivision of Written Sub-Corpora According to Tourist Board on Instagram

Instagram Corpus	Tokens	Words	% (Tokens)	Types/Token Ratio (TTR)
Tourism Ireland (@tourismireland)	7,670	1,818	18.2%	23.7
Destination Canada (@explorecanada)	14,984	3,554	35.6%	23.7
Tourism Western Australia (@westernaustralia)	19,444	3,294	46.2%	16.9

To analyze the strategies included in both visual and written content across corpora and establish connections between the findings, a media- and mode-contrastive table was drafted. This theoretical tool facilitated specifically a multilayered comparison between semiotic resources in terms of metafunctional meaning realization across channels (Mattei, 2023b, p. 8).² This table considers not only the specific semiotic affordances, or features, of each mode, but also the discourse-specific characteristics inherent in tourism

narratives (Dann, 1996), as well as the generic attributes and development based on communication objectives and semiotic meaning partition (Bateman, 2014; Bhatia, 1993; Maci, 2020). By employing the table as a theoretical foundation, it becomes possible to verify whether intrasemiotic and intersemiotic patterns of variable occurrences differ in terms of frequency and use across digital platforms. This analysis may uncover a distinct genre of Instagram tourism photography and discourse, with specific aims, conventions and audience in the marketing funnel of persuasion (Francesconi, 2014; Manca, 2016).

3.2. Annotation

The processes of categorization, identification and measurement of visual strategies' occurrences and variance through statistical analysis were supported by a tree tagging model adapted to tourism discourse and professional photography (Mai et al., 2011). The visual strategies included in the tagging system are based on the 'grammar of visual design' (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006) and grouped by metafunction. In particular, the model tracks decisions made by discourse specialists concerning (1) the selection of participants, the presence and type of 'processes' and 'settings' (macro-category: *Representation of Reality*), (2) the selection of camera shots and angles which, according to the literature, shape a particular power relationship (macro-category: *Relationship with the Audience*), and (3) the positioning and prominence, size of elements within the photograph (macro-category: *Composition*). The textual meaning or registerial variable of 'mode' brings together all findings and offers insight into how promotional narratives are realized on the two digital channels through varying uses, distribution of modes' materialities and semiotic partitioning of meaning, i.e., semiotic weight, role, and function (Stöckl et al., 2020).

The macro-categories directly linked to the three linguistic metafunctions are outlined in Appendix B (Mattei, 2023b). Each of the macro-categories comprises a series of sub-categories (or *macro-variables*) that group the choices or tagging possibilities in meaning construction (*main variables*).

The significance of this tool lies in its ability to precisely detect the specific type of visual strategy used in the promotional design of tourism images and measure its frequency across different communication channels. For instance, the distinction between action and reaction processes³ on the part of animate or inanimate entities and the preference for one of these constructs a specific representation of the tourist experience. On one hand, individuals engaged in activities symbolize agency, and provide concrete information about a tourist destination. On the other hand, reaction processes involving rear views of static subjects communicate a passive pre-conception of the experience and

foster specific perceptual and emotional expectations, mainly evoked through the act of observing people in contemplation (Francesconi, 2014; Debord, 1977).

This tool also allows for the empirical detection of the specific communicative task assigned to each mode. By means of strategies quantification, indeed, it enables the measurement of the degree of prominence and complexity of each semiotic mode, helping define its role—as central or subordinate, illustrative—and a relation of either equality or complementarity with accompanying modes.

3.3. SRI tagging software

The annotation system presented in this study was created using a freely available, web-based software technology known as *Statistically Reliable Image Tagging (SRI Tagging)*, an innovative resource for identifying and quantifying occurrences of strategies in visual data through customized taxonomies. SRI Tagging was developed to assist in complex manual tagging procedures on large visual corpora in collaboration with G. E. Pibiri, an Assistant Professor at Ca' Foscari University affiliated with the National Research Council in Italy (ISTI-CNR).

SRI Tagging was indeed developed to answer the need of linguistics and social semiotics scholars to categorize lexicogrammatical units in a similar way to corpus studies, and to manually test theoretical frameworks on different data. While notable scholarly efforts in corpus linguistics have led to the establishment of robust foundations for the empirical analysis of linguistic datasets, systematic annotation and research based on 'grammars' of visual design are currently in early stages of development. In a parallel manner, the growing presence of computational resources that perform automatic tagging based on Artificial Intelligence tasks has generated new models for the automatic identification of entities which, however, raise concerns about the accuracy and degree of adaptability of such models to the needs of the humanities and to critical discourse analysis. The following subsections will present and discuss the advantages of manual tagging with tailored models, also by comparing it to automatic annotation.

SRI Tagging software, created in 2020 and continuously improved, offers a user-friendly and openly accessible web-based platform for complex tree tagging and annotation of large datasets, making it accessible to scholars and students in various fields of humanities. This tool was indeed developed to encourage interdisciplinary collaboration and address the complexities of contemporary communication. Compared to other free tools like *UAM ImageTool* (O'Donnel, 2010) and *VGG Image Annotator* (Dutta & Zisserman, 2019),⁴ SRI Tagging allows for a smooth creation and adaptation of complex

tree tagging systems and performs efficiently during the annotation process, thanks to the implementation of C++ as backend programming language. It also enables on-site statistical analysis and the export of results to *Excel* in various formats. For these reasons, it may be considered to be similar to emerging, cutting-edge technologies for multimodal document analysis and collaborative projects such as *MAST* tool, which also offers templates of both taxonomies and relation types to support the annotation process (Cardoso & Cohn, 2022).⁵

While automatic entity recognition based on machine learning methods has become widely used and purchased for businesses and marketing studies,⁶ it often requires coding knowledge and can be complex to use and interpret. Manual annotation tools like *SRIT* provide researchers with more control and personalization in the annotation process, and may serve as means to develop categorization skills for subsequent (un)supervised machine learning tasks. Furthermore, manual labeling can be used to promote users' reflection on the role of subjective labeling in data coding and interpretation, and address biases in AI tools and procedures. *SRIT* has been successfully used in multimodality and digital humanities courses,⁷ promoting interest in multimodal research and facilitating collaborative efforts.

Figure 1.

Example of SRI Annotation Procedure

As mentioned, *SRI Tagging* provides discourse analysts with the opportunity to customize theory-based labels through an intuitive interface, eliminating the need for coding skills. This feature empowers both researchers and students to create, edit, and experiment with models and hierarchies of node

dependencies and taxonomies effortlessly. Thus, it serves the dual purpose of advancing scientific inquiry and facilitating pedagogical learning. Figure 1 (above) illustrates the annotation procedure.

Figure 2.
AND/OR Query on SRI Tagging

Despite the intrinsic role and research potential of taxonomies creation and adaptation, *SRIT* was designed primarily to enable the conduction of a wide range of on-site statistical analyses, also thanks to the efficient implementation of computational storage options. Similar to tools for corpus-based, linguistic research, *SRIT* enables statistical measurement of tag frequency and variance within and across corpora, identifying also tag co-occurrences (AND/OR queries) and ensuring the replicability of the coding procedure through inter-coder reliability measures—which is at the basis of any machine-learning and automatic tagging process. In particular, the software facilitates data and graphs export in .csv, Excel, and .pdf formats, thus enhancing transparency and enabling result replication and comparison. Additionally, it includes visualization tools powered by Jaccard and Weighted Hamming Indexes to augment research insights. Jaccard's index, in particular, compares tag choices between corpora created by the same user, and displays images with similar

features in each corpus for each query, demonstrating how similar visual techniques are implemented across different images. Images 2-4 show how AND/OR queries as well as Jaccard and Weighted Hamming indexes are computed.⁸

Figure 3.

The Visualization Tool Embedded in the Software Feature Jaccard Index

Compose a query using the model and see the results.

Jaccard Query

Clear

1

1

Figure 4.
The Calculation of Weighted Hamming Index on SRI Tagging

Direction of Gaze	0.708589
Towards the Represented Participant(s)	0.757669
Towards the Interactive Participant	0.941718
Camera Shot	0.039877
Close	0.917178
Medium	0.684049
Long	0.650307
Very Long	0.760736
Camera Angle	0.006135
Betw. Interactive and Represented Participant(s)	0.006135
Subjective Image	0.04908
Vertical Angle	0.06135
Low	0.797546
Eye-level	0.555215
High	0.782209
Very High	0.91411
Horizontal Angle	0.04908
Frontal	0.90184
Oblique	0.138037
Objective Image	0.957055
Direct Frontal Angle	0.972393
Perpendicular Top - Down Angle	0.984663
Perspective Techniques	0.070552
Absence of Background	0.966258
Blurred Background/Selective Focus	0.880368
Less Detailed/Colored Background	0.662577

In practical terms, *SRIT* empowers corpus linguists to craft and test hypotheses concerning the systematic presence of discourse narratives, by detecting visual features and uncovering correlations between data and metadata—such as the medium of dissemination, the designer of the message, the publishing year, etc. This facilitates the exploration of macro-context and micro-context relationships

and the identification of emerging discourse trends. An example of its application is demonstrated in sections 3.1. and 3.2., which showcase results from the DH study for which *SRIT* was designed.

Moreover, *SRIT* enables the on-site performance of inter-annotator agreement calculations to ensure the objectivity and consistency of the tagging procedure and discard the hypothesis of agreement by chance. Following Bateman's guidelines for empirical research in multimodal discourse analysis, the software incorporates Scott's *pi* inter-coder consistency measure (Bateman et al., 2017). Inter-coder reliability measures are often implemented to calculate the agreement rate between tagging choices made by two different annotators, who (1) tag the same set of images using (2) the same tagging system and following (3) the same set of instructions independently. This measure guarantees reproducible results, qualitative interpretations, and method replicability if the threshold value of 0.7 is reached. In the current study, the resulting average reliability value was 0.894.

4. Results

The possibility of exporting data into other tools not only enhances the transparency of the tagging procedure, but also facilitates the replication and comparison of research findings. Additionally, it is crucial to perform advanced and exploratory statistics that may be implemented for the analysis of similar datasets. To achieve these objectives, *SRIT* was equipped with a series of export options, including yes/no tables for inter-annotator measurement in *R*. Sections 4.1 and 4.2 show the process of generating and confirming data-driven hypotheses about the role of media in influencing data clusterings, i.e., the material forms patterns of visual data. This technique creates fertile ground for evidence-based interpretations concerning the reasons behind such phenomenon (section 4.3).⁹

4.1. Statistical hypothesis testing in *R*

In the DH study presented in this paper, a series of quantitative analyses were carried out to measure the degree of similarity and variance in terms of occurrences of visual strategies across channels. As attested by recent scholarly work in linguistics and empirical semiotic studies (Gries, 2021; Bateman et al., 2021) researchers may opt for one or more of the following measures:

- Frequency rates and means (Descriptive statistics)
- One-way *ANOVA*, Chi-Square, Principal Component Analysis, Correspondence Analysis (Inferential and exploratory statistics)

- Scott's *pi*, Cohen's *kappa*, and Krippendorff's *alpha* (Intercoder reliability)

Table 4*Tools for the Study of Multimodal Corpora*

Multimodal corpus techniques and tools	Corpus Linguistics (and SFL)	Image tagging
Frequency	Wordlists	Percentages and frequency rates
Statistical significance— Variance	Keyword analysis (Keyness)	<i>Chi-square (R)</i>
Correlation	Collocation analysis	Correspondence Analysis (<i>R</i>)
Annotation and (Inter-coder)	Automatic <i>POS</i> tagging	Scott's <i>Pi (SRIT)</i>
Reliability	Manual classification	Cohen's <i>kappa (R)</i>
	Cohen's <i>kappa (R)</i>	Krippendorff's <i>alpha (R)</i>

The analysis of the visual corpora carried out in this study thus seeks to provide tools and methods that are similar to and reflect the aims of Corpus Linguistics, as shown in Table 4 (above).

The initial phase of the study involved the extraction of raw data, which included tag occurrences for each image in different sub-corpora. The grouping of occurrences of each variable according to channel on *Excel* allowed for the conduction of frequency analysis and then one-way *ANOVA* in *Jamovi*, to calculate the mean occurrences of each tag across channel sub-corpora. This process helped identify statistically significant variations in the use of specific tags across different channels, with *p*-values < 0.5 indicating that the observed variations were not due to chance but rather reflected patterns in specific social practices (Şahin & Aybek, 2019).

The results were then cross-referenced with *Chi-Square* and contingency tables, after the process of identification of significant correlations between tags conducted in *R*. In the current study, the *Chi-square* test confirmed the hypothesis that the features identified in the visual corpora differ in frequency and use based on the dissemination channel and its specific role in the marketing funnel of persuasion (Manca, 2016). In particular, a statistical significance testing identified variables with unusually high frequencies deviating from the average value (mean), while the computation of a contingency table grouped occurrences of each feature of the tagging system based on the categorical variables, i.e., Instagram and website channels. This table facilitated the calculation of residuals for each feature (tag), indicating the amount of deviation or error for each variable by subtracting the expected frequency from the observed frequency.¹⁰

Table 5
List of Selected p-Values

Experiential meaning Variables (tags)	Statistically significant values (Chi-square with alpha reliability score > 0.6)
Direct Presence of Living Beings	0.00878
Process of Action	0.00000
Animal Life (A)	0.00202
Livestock (A)	0.01028
Animal Life (R)	0.00238
Desert/Shrubs	0.00000
Mountains	0.00627
Forest	0.01327
Marine Environment	0.00778
Artificial	0.00271
Town/Village	0.00557
Gastronomic	0.00093
Analytical	0.00181

Table 5 (above) provides a comparison of these variables and reports a selected list of low *p*-values. Low *p*-values indicate the model's fitness for predicting response variable values, and specifically the presence of variables with unexpectedly higher frequencies. Here, the predictor variable is the channel, and the response variables are the tags in the tagging system. As can be seen from the tables, variables showing a pattern of unusually higher frequency and thus contributing to a specific construction of both tourist experiences and viewer relationships are tags related to the (1) presence of living beings, (2) action and (3) reaction processes, and (4) settings.

To better understand the results provided by the *Chi*-square test, we can also look at descriptive statistics values. If we look, for example, at the *Tourism Ireland* sub-corpora and their relative frequencies¹¹ reported in Figure 5, we notice differences in all main categories of the ideational metafunction. In particular, humans performing action processes appear in in 8,7% of Instagram images, compared to 40% in the website sub-corpus, with a predominance of non-transactional actions (20%) that do not show what the goal,¹² or objective of the process is. Additionally, Instagram is characterized by a larger presence of animals performing mostly reaction processes (9,5% versus 2,5% on the website) with a non-transactional nature (13,5% versus 6,5%) and in entirely natural settings (96% versus 64,5%). The gaze is thus directed outside the picture, either towards an indefinite point or the viewer (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006).

Figure 5.
Relative Frequencies of the Tags of the First Metafunction in the Tourism Ireland Sub-Corpora

This analysis further stimulates interest in the role of the gaze, the distance as well as perspective adopted to represent the participants and the settings, which are analyzed through the *Relationship with the audience* macro-category. If we look at the sum of the relative frequencies across channel corpora (Figure 6),¹³ we notice that the gaze, in website corpora, is mostly directed towards a participant concretely represented, i.e., visible, in the picture (86,4%).

Since Instagram images feature fewer living beings or, in general, beings that are not close enough to the camera to have their process identified, the presence of the gaze is understandably lower compared to the website (65,6%). However, the presence of similar values in the sub-category *Towards the interactive participant* across channels (22% and 21,3%) suggests that the gaze directed at the viewer is, on Instagram, as frequent as in website communication, thus potentially indicating a preference for this type of gaze in Instagram pictures. In the categories of shot and angle, we notice that close and medium shots are more often adopted in website imagery (66,8% and 118,9% on websites; 30,3% and 66,7% on Instagram), together with eye-level angles (143,4%), whereas Instagram shows more images with long shots (117,5%

versus 55,5%) and very high angles (50,7% versus 13,2%). The higher presence of top-down angles in websites (20% versus 7,8%) is due to the larger presence of informative content and objective, conceptual imagery like maps and diagrams on websites.

Figure 6.

Sum of the Relative Frequencies of the Tags Related the Second Metafunction

4.2. Exploratory statistics

The script used for correspondence analysis (CA) and inter-corpora visual correlations provided further confirmation of strong associations between the categorical variables of channels and a series of tags. Additionally, it revealed no statistically significant differences in the use of most visual strategies across different tourist boards.¹⁴

CA is a statistical technique that uses counts and metadata to cluster together variables that tend to co-occur in a multidimensional space. Figure 7 visually illustrates the relationships between variables within the first metafunction, including their distribution based on channel metadata. The figure indicates distinctions between Instagram and website visual narratives in terms of how they use and combine narrative features, including the type of action, subject or object, and setting. Indeed, if we look at the tags clustering around the

structured into three parts that explore the visual representation of the gaze and tourist tropes through a carefully selected sample of images.

4.3.1. Settings and human footprint

The Instagram corpus primarily

consists of images showcasing remote, pristine landscapes and natural details with minimal human presence. Images 1-3 exemplify this trend which, according to existing literature, is leveraged to spark imagination and construct a sense of untouched beauty (Uzzel, 1984), with Image 3 highlighting the spectacular nature of a sunset reflected symmetrically in the water—and in which humans are backlighted. In contrast, website images depict more ordinary holiday experiences, as they include social interactions (Image 6), everyday routines (Image 5), or crowded tourist activities (Image 4) in artificial settings.

Image 2.

Image Taken from the IG, Western Australia Sub-Corpus

Image 1.

Image Taken from the IG, Western Australia Sub-Corpus

Image 3.

Image Taken from the IG, Western Australia Sub-Corpus

This variance suggests a focus on different aspects of the tourist destination. While website images emphasize the attractiveness and exclusivity of organized tours and package holidays, including ‘group bonding’, mass activities in popular sites (Urry and Larsen, 2011), Instagram images highlight the spectacular observation of untouched landscapes from extraordinary vantage points, by also using aesthetically pleasing design techniques. This approach aims to capture attention through beauty and inspiration, emphasizing landscapes devoid of human influence.

Website images seem, therefore, to serve a more practical purpose of providing information, while social media images aim to stimulate imagination. Humans, when present in Instagram images, are rarely the focal point. For instance, in Image 3, the main focus of the image is the sunset, which also creates a sense of exclusive connection with nature by highlighting close experiences with animals typical of Western Australia.

4.3.2. Gazing practices

In images 7-11 on Instagram, there's a notable distinction in how semiotic resources are used; indeed, while images 7-8 depict structured, comfortable recreational experiences with a focus on transactional actions and reactions—creating a sense of closeness and

Image 4.

Image Taken from the Website, Western Australia Sub-Corpus

Image 5.

Image Taken from the Website, Tourism Ireland Sub-Corpus

Image 6.

Image Taken from the Website, Tourism Ireland Sub-Corpus

identification through close-up shots –images 9-11 showcase reactions aimed at sparking desire through contemplation of natural beauty (Campbell, 1987).

Image 7.

Image Taken from the Website, Tourism Ireland Sub-Corpus

Image 8.

Image Taken from the Website, Tourism Ireland Sub-Corpus

Image 9.

Image Taken from the IG, Western Australia Sub-Corpus

Image 10.

Image Taken from the IG, Destination Canada Sub-Corpus

The overall results of the corpus analysis show that Instagram images favor the representation of tourists merging with the wild nature, which creates a romantic connection, and stimulates the identification with the idea of being a wanderer, sometimes strategically captured from high vantage points for added appeal. Alternatively, images construct carefully curated and enchanting

realities, in which the participants are so captured by the surrounding environment that they do not engage with the camera and disconnect with the viewer. The IG use of rear views (*non-transactional reactions*) and distant poses in solitary settings, indeed, acts as a marketing strategy, which invites viewers to wonder and desire to experience what the subjects are feeling (Francesconi, 2014).

Furthermore, the inclusion of indexical references like swimwear or life jackets taps into subconscious and socially driven needs such as self-actualization and sexual arousal, often linked to breaking taboos or venturing into the unknown. These references symbolize emotional states and social conditions, transferring these feelings and desires to the viewers of the photographs (Dann, 1996).

Image 11.
Image Taken from the IG, Tourism Ireland Sub-Corpus

4.3.3. Taming the typical: Issues of anthropomorphosis and dehumanization

As was shown throughout these sections, gazes may be constructed also through the representation of gazes. Statistical analysis combined with qualitative insights provided additional information in this respect and confirmed that Instagram aims to engage viewers in the visual exploration of untouched natural landscapes from a detached tourist perspective. Instagram images, indeed, often feature distant, captivating views of unspoiled nature, emphasizing the absence of human presence. For example, an image with a bear as the focal point of the picture (Image 12) symbolizes the wildness and natural beauty of the environment, suggesting a connection between nature and tourists. The use of close-up shots and eye-level angles, when related to representations of wildlife's gazes also evokes affection and fosters a sense of human connection with the animal (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2006). In contrast, website images focus on practical aspects, like a smiling young cook preparing local cuisine, sparking a desire to participate in such intimate experiences and savor delicious, regional food (Image 13).

In summary, the findings reveal that Instagram and website pictures add a sense of uniqueness and authenticity to the tourist experience in different ways, encouraging viewers to either imagine exclusive interactions with nature and animals (*timeless* and *strangerhood* strategy) or the range of

services and organized activities (*play strategy*) proposed by the travel boards, in an attempt to showcase what can be done and ultimately persuade tourists to purchase holiday packages and seek further guidance.¹⁶ The importance of aesthetics and complex design in IG pictures, additionally, confirms the different partitioning of labor, or role, on IG, thus leading to the identification of a specific genre of communication on Instagram (Bateman, 2014).

In the context of Instagram, indeed, the image seems to play a primary role in fostering meaning elaboration and attracting the attention, and this was further confirmed by the textual analysis that revealed the presence of more informative concrete on the websites, with the text serving a subordinate function to anchor and complement the message already conveyed by the image (Mattei, forthcoming). Conversely, on the website, this semiotic partitioning of meaning is reversed, and the image takes on a supportive role as an illustrative element of the message conveyed by the written text. We may argue, then, that tourist imagery on the official website caters to an audience already interested in the services offered and seeking concrete information for holiday planning rather than just inspiration—usually provided by visually appealing and evocative landscapes (Garrod, 2009; Manovich, 2017).

Image 12.

Image Taken from the IG, Destination Canada Sub-Corpus

Image 13.

Image Taken from the Website, Destination Canada Sub-Corpus

5. Conclusion

Compared to automatic entity detection, manual annotation was shown to support analysts in the detection of specific semiotic resources within the

visual mode in a strictly supervised environment. Manual annotation may also represent the first step in the learning curve towards an understanding of how machine learning and AI operate, as it provides insights into how data may be categorized—with non-biased procedures and controlled collection of data—by humans. It allows to retain full control of the procedure for specific research and pedagogical purposes, also with the possibility of creating tailored tagging systems based on theoretical notions (such as that of *metafunction*) without any previous coding knowledge, allowing individuals to reflect on details detected manually in visual meaning. Thus, it represents a precious tool for raising awareness of computer-machine readable data biases that has implications on a large scale in the digital world. A recent example is TikTok content creators incorporating manual labeling of AI-generated content to accumulate sufficient data for machine-learning-based automatic detection.¹⁷ Without awareness of the potential of manual tagging and understanding the material characteristics of artificially generated content, however, 'crowdsourced' tagged content might introduce biases that are subsequently replicated by computers. This situation can lead to a troubling overlap between content related to real events and individuals and fictitious content, potentially resulting in the failure to identify fake news.

Moreover, manual annotation excels in detecting specific features such as processes, shots, angles, visual weights, and their combinations, which may pose challenges for AI solutions. In summary, manual annotation emerges as a crucial tool for in-depth visual analysis, bias awareness, and fostering digital literacy as well as agency in an age of machine learning and AI (Christiansen, 2017; Raffone, 2023).

This project has both limitations and promising directions for future research. First, further investigation is needed to determine whether the statistical correlation between tags and digital media may be attributed to the primary communication goals of each platform, the sociodemographic characteristics of their audiences, and the evolving needs and behaviors of the postmodern era. Such work could involve marketing inquiries and surveys to verify IG followers' intentions and changes in perception and behavior after prolonged exposure to promotional content, combined with neurolinguistic or psycholinguistic studies.

Future research should also focus on testing the same tagging model or a new version on the same or new datasets, to enhance the reproducibility and replicability of the tagging procedure. Due to the increasingly irreversible environmental crisis and in line with current trend of eco-tourism research, the framework developed for this study could be applied to develop narratives that challenge the prevailing consumerist ideology, which portrays humans as exploiters of natural resources. Constructing an equitable relationship

between humans and nature might motivate tourists to actively engage in sustainable activities that protect natural ecosystems and endangered biodiversity.

In conclusion, the interdisciplinary field of digital humanities holds significant social and academic importance, by offering reliable solutions and objective insights into complex social phenomena. If taken into account during the conduction of discourse analysis, it may deepen our critical understanding of ideological positions and biased constructs in our society, ultimately encouraging individuals to work collectively for long-term change and improved, collective wellbeing.

Notes

1. Additional results on the analysis of the visual corpora presented in this study are reported in Mattei (2024), while computational and discourse analysis of text materials is available in Mattei (forthcoming). To gain some insights into how the text was analyzed and categorized, please see Mattei (2023b).
2. For reasons of space, the table is not included here. For an overview of the comparative framework, see Mattei (2023b).
3. In Kress and van Leeuwen's *Grammar of Visual Design*, reaction processes involve the static observation on the part of a living subject (*participant*). Such processes usually denote perceptual and mental activities.
4. <https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/software/via/>. This powerful tool was developed by the Visual Geometry Group at Oxford University, together with software for visual datasets queries (VGG Image Search Engine) and machine learning methods (VGG Image Classification Engine). While the description of each one of these tools is outside the scope of this paper, the review of existing effective tools is beneficial to readers seeking options that align with their specific interests.
5. Please see <https://www.visuallanguagelab.com/research> and <https://www.visuallanguagelab.com/multimodality> for further information.
6. See for example Vertex AI or Cloud Factory: <https://cloud.google.com/vertex-ai?hl=it>; <https://bitly.ws/VBJL>.
7. The software has been used so far at Verona and Bremen Universities.
8. Please see Matsuoka and Ito (2024) for further information on the Weighted Hamming Index.
9. The list of the statistically significant variables related to the interpersonal and textual metafunctions is available in Mattei (2023a).

10. In Chi square analysis, the square of the difference is then computed and divided by the expected cell frequency. The contingency tables showing the residuals with respect to channel metadata are not reported here, but may be visualized in Mattei (2023a). The tag counts are also available in an open-access format in Mattei (2024).
11. Relative frequencies (see Appendix C) are the frequencies calculated by the software in relation to the total number of the images of the corpus. This is because in manual visual annotation, compared to linguistic corpus tokenization and POS automatic annotation, tags need to be assigned to each image id to be quantified. This measure is, thus, a way of studying the dispersion of tags across images and sub-corpora and exploring the nature of each image in relation to its metadata, namely the agency and the channel, as occurs in other statistical tests (see Mattei, 2024) and in entity recognition. The software, however, also allows to calculate the number of occurrences of a particular tag in relation to an overarching category.
12. In narrative representations, actions are represented by a vector—like an arrow, or an imaginary line. In (static) reaction processes, the imaginary line is usually the direction of the gaze.
13. In this graph, cumulative frequencies of each tag (specifically, sums of relative frequencies) are provided in relation to the channel. The sum of counts in descriptive statistics is not indeed reliable if the size of each corpus is different.
14. Exploratory and inferential analyses (Mattei, 2024; Mattei, forthcoming) proved that the most statistically significant differences were at the platform level. This does not necessarily mean, however, that there are no inter-agency differences deserving critical attention. While cross-cultural analysis is not the main aim of the paper, future research might engage with questions related to the identification and influence of specific cultural traits in visual tourism discourse, as previous work has done in terms of linguistic analysis (Manca, 2018).
15. 15. The images published in this study and posted online by the travel boards were reproduced in accordance with the principles of fair use. In 2019, the three boards were contacted to secure permission for collecting and analyzing their visual and written materials for research purposes. While permissions were received at the time, only Tourism Ireland responded to recent follow-ups regarding image reproduction for scholarly work. As per fair use, the use of these materials is aimed at criticism, comment, and scholarship, reflecting non-commercial educational purposes. Special thanks go to Tourism Ireland for their

continued support, as initially granted in 2019 for the author's doctoral research.

16. This was confirmed also by both qualitative and quantitative linguistic analysis (Mattei 2023a; Mattei, 2023b).
17. Please see this site: <https://newsroom.tiktok.com/en-us/new-labels-for-disclosing-ai-generated-content> for further information.

The Author

Elena Mattei (Email: elena.mattei@unive.it) is a Postdoctoral Research Fellow at Ca' Foscari University of Venice, where she is working on the National Research Project DIETALY (*Destination Italy in English Translation and language over the Years*) in collaboration with the Italian National Tourist Board. Shortlisted for the *Paul Fortier* Prize, she is publishing a Routledge monograph on tourism discourse and collaborates with John Bateman. Her research interests include the annotation and statistical analysis of tourism multimodal corpora through systemic functional linguistics frameworks. Her main objective is to promote regenerative travel, a topic discussed also in interviews with *Randstad Research* and *La Repubblica*.

References

- Ayeh, J. K., Suryana, M., & Amalia, S. (2012). Perceptions and strategies of hospitality and tourism practitioners on social media: An exploratory study. *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism*, 35(21), 1-12.
- Barthes, R. (1999). The rhetoric of the image. In J. Evans & S. Hall (Eds.), *Visual culture: The reader* (pp. 33-40). Sage Publications.
- Bateman, J. A. (2014). Genre in the age of multimodality: Some conceptual refinements for practical analysis. In P. E. Allori, J. A. Bateman & V. K. Bhatia (Eds.), *Evolution in genres: Emergence, variation, multimodality* (pp. 237-269). Peter Lang.
- Bateman, J. A. (2018). Peircean semiotics and multimodality: Towards a new synthesis. *Multimodal Communication*, 7(1), 1-24.
- Bateman, J. A. (2019). Towards critical multimodal discourse analysis: A response to Ledin and Machin. *Critical Discourse Studies*, 16(5), 531-539.

- Bateman, J. A. (2021). Dimensions of materiality. In J. Pflaeging, J. Wildfeuer & J. A. Bateman (Eds.), *Empirical multimodality research: Methods, evaluations, implications* (pp. 35-64). Walter de Gruyter.
- Bateman, J. A., O'D Veloso, F., & Lau, Y. L. (2021). On the track of visual style: A diachronic study of page composition in comics and its functional motivation. *Visual Communication, 20*(2), 209-247.
- Bateman, J., Wildfeuer, J., & Hiippala, T. (2017). *Multimodality: Foundations, research and analysis: A problem-oriented introduction*. De Gruyter Mouton.
- Bhatia, V. K. (1993). *Analyzing genre language use in professional settings*. Longman.
- Bianchi, F. (2017). The social tricks of advertising: Discourse strategies of English-speaking tour operators on Facebook. *Iperstoria, 10*, 3-32.
- Campbell, C. (1987). *The romantic ethic and the spirit of modern consumerism*. Basil Blackwell.
- Cardoso, B., & Cohn, N. (2022). The multimodal annotation software tool (MAST). *Proceedings of the 13th Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2022)*, (pp. 6822-6828).
- Christiansen, M. S. (2017). Multimodal L2 composition: EAP in the digital era. *International Journal of Language Studies, 11*(3), 53-72.
- Cope, B., & Kalantzis, M. (2009). A grammar of multimodality. *International Journal of Learning, 16*(2), 361-425.
- Dann, G. (1996). *The language of tourism: A sociolinguistic perspective*. CAB International.
- Debord, G. (1977). *The society of the spectacle*. Black & Red.
- Dutta, A., & Zisserman, A. (2019). The VIA annotation software for images, audio and video. In L. Amsaleg, B. Huet, M. Larson, G. Gravier, H. Hung, C.-W. Ngo, W. T. Ooi (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 27th ACM international conference on multimedia* (pp. 2276-2279). Nice: Association for Computing Machinery.

- Francesconi, S. (2014). *Reading tourism texts: A multimodal analysis*. Channel View Publications.
- Garrod, B. (2009). Understanding the relationship between tourism destination imagery and tourist photography. *Journal of Travel Research*, 47(3), 346-368.
- Gotti, M., Maci, S., & Sala, M. (Eds.). (2017). *Ways of seeing, ways of being: Representing the voices of tourism*. Peter Lang.
- Gries, S. T. (2021). *Statistics for linguistics with R: A practical introduction*. Walter de Gruyter.
- Hallett, R. W., & Kaplan-Weinger, J. (2010). *Official tourism websites: A discourse analysis perspective*. Channel View Publications.
- Halliday, M. A. K., & Matthiessen, C. M. I. M. (2014). *Introduction to functional grammar*. Routledge.
- Hays, S., Page, S. J., & Buhalis, D. (2013). Social media as a destination marketing tool: Its use by national tourism organisations. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 16(3), 211-239.
- Huang, Y., & Su, S. (2018). Motives for Instagram use and topics of interest among young adults. *Future internet*, 10(8), 1-12.
- Insulander, E., & Lindstrand, F. (2013). Towards a social and ethical view of semiosis: Examples from the museum. In M. Böck & N. Pachler (Eds.), *Multimodality and social semiosis: Communication, meaning-making and learning in the work of Gunther Kress* (pp. 239-250). Routledge.
- Kilgariff, A., Baisa, V., Bušta, J., Jakubíček, M., Kovář, V., Michelfeit, J., Rychlý, P., & Suchomel, V. (2014). The sketch engine: Ten years on. *Lexicography*, 1(1), 7-36.
- Kress, G. (2010). *Multimodality: A social semiotic approach to contemporary communication*. Routledge.
- Kress, G., & van Leeuwen, T. (2006). *Reading images: The grammar of visual design*. Routledge.
- Krippendorff, K. (2004). *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology*. Sage.

- Leung, D., Law, R., van Hoof, H., & Buhalis, D. (2013). Social media in tourism and hospitality: A literature review. *Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing*, 30(1-2), 3-22.
- Maci, S. M. (2020). *English tourism discourse: Insights into the professional, promotional, and digital language of tourism*. Hoepli Editore.
- Mai, L., Le, H., Niu, Y., & Liu, F. (2011). Rule of thirds detection from photographs. *IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia* (pp. 91-96). IEEE.
- Manca, E. (2016). *Persuasion in tourism discourse: Methodologies and models*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Manca, E. (2018). Verbal techniques of the language of tourism across cultures: An analysis of five official tourist websites. In E. Manca (Ed.), *Innovative perspectives on tourism discourse* (pp. 91-110). IGI Global.
- Manca, E. (2018). Verbal techniques of the language of tourism across cultures: An analysis of five official tourist websites. In M. Bielenia-Grajewska & E. Cortes de los Rios (Eds.), *Innovative perspectives on tourism discourse* (pp. 91-110). IGI Global.
- Manovich, L. (2017). Instagram and contemporary image. *Manovich.net*.
- Matsuoka, T., & Ito, S. (2024). Maximization of minimum weighted Hamming distance between set pairs. *Proceedings of the 15th Asian Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR 222* (pp. 895-910). PMLR.
- Mattei, E. (2023a). *Multimodal corpus analysis of digital tourism narratives: A data-driven approach based on systemic functional linguistics and social semiotics*. (PhD dissertation). University of Verona.
- Mattei, E. (2023b). Theory and method for the statistical investigation of multimodal promotional practices in the digital era: A data-driven approach based on systemic functional linguistics and social semiotics. *IDEAH*, 3(2), 1-32.
- Mattei, E. (2024). Approaching tourism communication with empirical multimodality: Exploratory analysis of Instagram and website photography through data-driven labeling. *Frontiers in Communication*, 9, 1355406.

- Mattei, E. (forthcoming). *The language of persuasion on Instagram: A systemic functional grammar of multimodal tourism discourse*. Routledge.
- Mattei, E. (forthcoming). *The meaning of images: Testing the grammar of visual design on Instagram travel photography*. De Gruyter.
- McEnery, T., & Hardie, A. (2011). *Corpus linguistics: Method, theory and practice*. Cambridge University Press.
- Messaris, P. (1997). *Visual persuasion: The role of images in advertising*. Sage.
- Mitchell, W. J. T., & Mitchell, W. J. T. (1994). *Picture theory: Essays on verbal and visual representation*. University of Chicago Press.
- O'Donnel, M. (2010). *UAM Image Tool (Version 2.0)*. <https://www.wagsoft.com/ImageTool>
- Pflaeging, J., Wildfeuer, J., & Bateman, J. A. (Eds.). (2021). *Empirical multimodality research: Methods, evaluations, implications*. Mouton de Gruyter.
- Raffone, A. (2023). Combining critical linguistics methods and novel pedagogies: Digital storytelling and discourse analysis for social change. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 17(2), 1-24.
- Şahin, M. D., & Aybek, E. C. (2019). *Jamovi: An easy to use statistical software for the social scientists*. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education*, 6(4), 670-692.
- Sayers, J. (2018). *The Routledge companion to media studies and digital humanities*. Routledge.
- Shuqair, S., & Cragg, P. (2017). The immediate impact of Instagram posts on changing the viewers' perceptions towards travel destinations. *Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Business and Social Studies*, 3(2), 1-12.
- Stöckl, H., Caple, H., & Pflaeging, J. (2020). Shifts towards image-centricity in contemporary multimodal practices: An introduction. In H. Stöckl, H. Caple & J. Pflaeging (Eds.), *Shifts towards image-centricity in contemporary multimodal practices* (pp. 1-18). Routledge.
- Taylor, C., & Marchi, A., (Eds.). (2018). *Corpus approaches to discourse: A critical review*. Routledge.

Tomlinson, T. (2007). *The culture of speed: The coming of immediacy*. Sage.

Urry, J., & Larsen, J. (2011). *The tourist gaze 3.0*. Sage Publications.

Uzzel, D. (1984). An alternative structuralist approach to the psychology of tourism marketing. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 11, 79-99.

Zeng, B. (2013). Social media in tourism. *Journal of Tourism & Hospitality*, 2(1), 1-2.

Appendix A: An overview of Kress' sociosemiotic approach to visual meaning analysis followed by preliminary empirical adaptations

The Grammar of Visual Design	Ideational/Experiential	Interpersonal	Textual
(Meta)functions of visual mode (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2006)	Reception, internalization and construction of worldviews	Communication and negotiation of worldviews and related attitudes, emotions, evaluations	Visual arrangement of information in a coherent and cohesive way: 1) intrasemiotically; 2) intersemiotically; 3) by taking into account the social context (including the medium, the participants, the ideology)
Critical questions for visual analysis (Kress, 2010; Cope & Kalantzis, 2009)	Who are the participants? Are they engaged in some activities in particular settings?	What is the purpose of the message? What is the particular type of power relationship between me, the producer of the message and the elements depicted?	What is the context of communication? Whose interests are served through the communication of these meanings? What role do image and text play in the construction of meaning?
Empirical detection (Mattei, 2023b; Pflaeging et al., 2021)	How are the participants pictured—moving or standing still? Are they animate or inanimate? Can the gaze be detected? Where is it directed? Which environment surrounds the participants?	Is there a gaze directed towards the viewer or towards some entity in the picture that can be seen—or that cannot be seen? What kind of shot and angle are implemented?	Which mode is predominant or necessary? How are modes visually arranged? What elements of the picture and text stand out, and why? How are participants pictured—in terms of size, disposition, color? What perspective and aesthetics techniques are employed? Why might the overall arrangement at the intra- and intersemiotic level be effective? What sociological, economic, or political reasons might be there?

Appendix B: Tree tagging system for the annotation of tourism images building on Halliday's three metafunctions

Macro-Category (grouping features that are always selected)	Sub-Category (Macro-Variables) (grouping features that are often selected)	Main Variables (choices)
Representation of Reality	Participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Humans ● Animals
	Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Action ● Reaction ● Transactional action/reaction ● Non-transactional action/reaction
	Setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Natural ● Artificial ● Cultural ● Historical ● Gastronomic ● Analytical
Relationship with the Audience	Direction of Gaze	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Towards the represented participant ● Towards the interactive participant
	Camera Shot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Close ● Medium ● Long ● Very long
	Camera Angle (Perspective)	Subjective Image <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Vertical angle (low, eye-level, high, very high) ● Horizontal angle (frontal, oblique) Objective Image <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Direct Frontal angle ● Top-down angle
Composition	Space Distribution	Rule of Thirds <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One point, more points ● Scenic rule of thirds (water, land, sky) ● Lines (horizontal, vertical) Other techniques <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Centric ● Polarization ● Symmetry
	Visual Flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Leading line(s) ● Connecting dots ● Framework
	Visual Weight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Landscape element ● Represented living participant ● Object

Appendix C: Relative frequencies of tags (%)**1. Ideational metafunction**

Tag	TI_IG	EC_IG	WA_IG	TI_WS	EC_WS	WA_WS
Direct Presence of Living Beings	33,3333	61,1111	53,3707	57	65	56,3291
Animal Life (A)	9,5238	6,1111	11,2359	5	5	7,5949
Humans (A)	8,7301	27,7777	14,6067	40	46,875	32,2784
Type of Action	16,6666	32,2222	23,5955	42	50	37,9746
Transactional Action	10,3174	21,6666	7,3033	23	30	13,9240
Non-transactional Action	6,3492	11,1111	16,2921	20	21,25	24,0506
Animal Life (R)	9,5238	9,4444	6,1797	2,5	2,5	1,8987
Humans (R)	9,5238	21,6666	25,2808	14,5	12,5	15,8227
Transactional Reaction	4,7619	15	15,7303	10,5	6,25	9,4936
Non-transactional Reaction	13,4920	16,1111	13,4831	6,5	8,75	8,8607
Natural	96,0317	79,4444	94,3820	64,5	48,75	77,8481
Artificial	15,0793	37,2222	18,5393	28	30	20,8860
Cultural	25,3968	19,4444	8,4269	33,5	21,875	13,2911
Historical	32,5396	9,4444	2,2471	25,5	10,625	1,8987
Gastronomic	0	1,1111	0,5617	7	8,75	10,1265
Analytical	0	0	1,1235	11	15	3,7974
Activities	15,07936	40	28,6516	44	51,875	34,8101

2. Interpersonal metafunction

Tag	TI_IG	EC_IG	WA_IG	TI_WS	EC_WS	WA_WS	IG_sum_%	WS_sum_%
Towards the Represented Participant(s)	14,2857	30,5555	20,7865	30,5	30,625	25,3164	65,6277	86,4414
Towards the Interactive Participant	7,1428	7,7777	7,30337	5	10	6,3291	22,2240	21,3291
Close	0,7936	16,6666	12,9213	14	27,5	25,3164	30,3816	66,8164
Medium	14,2857	33,3333	19,1011	41,5	35	42,4050	66,7201	118,9050
Long	46,0317	36,6666	34,8314	28,5	15	12,0253	117,5298	55,52531
Very Long	38,8888	13,3333	33,1460	15,5	11,25	17,0886	85,3682	43,8386
Low	18,2539	23,3333	12,3595	22,5	19,375	15,1898	53,9468	57,0648
Eye-level	37,3015	43,8888	32,0224	46,5	40,625	56,3291	113,2129	143,4541
High	25,3968	20,5555	25,8426	22,5	21,875	12,0253	71,7950	56,4003
Very High	18,2539	10	22,4719	2,5	3,75	6,9620	50,7258	13,2120
Frontal	8,7301	14,4444	10,1123	10,5	9,375	11,3924	33,2869	31,2674
Oblique	90,4761	82,7777	81,4606	83,5	75,625	80,3797	254,7146	239,5047
Direct Frontal Angle	0,7936	0,55555	1,1235	4	3,75	0,6329	2,4728	8,3829
Perpendicular Top -Down Angle	0	1,6666	6,1797	2,5	11,25	6,3291	7,8464	20,0791